

Cultural Identity of Women in Nagaland

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Abstract In this world, every individual who belongs to a civilized community or society, owns a particular set of ideologies. An ideology is the commonly accepted norms cherished by all the members of a particular group along with every minute aspect of their lives. Cultural identity is the accumulative behavior exhibited in the practice of the accepted values and ideals of a society. Nagaland is the north-eastern state of India; home to seventeen major Naga ethnic groups, only Indian state which has negative population growth. Nagaland, the land of cultural diversity; having distinct customs, language and lifestyle of each tribe, was a district of Assam until 1957 and became a full-fledged state on 1st December 1963. The condition of Naga women, similar to the mainland India is deplorable but somewhat better than their traditional life. Naga women possess a distinct cultural identity which is preserved, contained and deep-seated in the cultural and ethnic values of their communities.

Keywords Culture, Cultural Identity, Tribe, Contribution, Perspective, Women.

Introduction Culture is a set of customs, beliefs, rules and art of living of a particular group of people which distinguishes them from others. Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary defines culture as – “**the customs and beliefs, art, way of life and social organization of a particular country or group...**” (Hornby 377). Cultural Identity is the combination of everything that constitutes a person's social surroundings which they inhabit for generations and assimilation of it in every aspect of their lives. It is the cultural environment which makes individuals act accordingly and identify themselves to their customs and norms, have a sense of belongingness; share a common code of conduct. Collier and Thomas define cultural identity as “**Identification with and perceived acceptance into a group that has a shared system of symbols and meanings as well as norms/rules for conduct**” (113). Thus, cultural identity is a system that constitutes every component of the overall personality and existence of a person. Nagaland is a north-eastern state of India, rich in cultural diversity and wealth of nature. It was formally inaugurated on 1st December 1963 and became the 16th state of India. Nagaland is a home to 17 major and other minor indigenous tribes having their own distinct customs and beliefs. Naga people rely primarily on agriculture to run the family and it was chiefly the responsibility of a woman to take up the tasks of farming and sowing. Here, women fulfill most of the duties of a household; from feeding the newborns to working on the field. A Naga woman has to be well versed in every activity assigned to a female in their culture.

Objective of study The present article aims to evaluate how the cultural identity of Naga women has been transformed and developed by their own incessant efforts in the course of time.

Review of Literature

Tracing the history of Naga women reveals that they held a very significant place in the social and cultural framework of Nagaland. Different tribes of Nagaland have their own unique customs and practices. Earlier these tribes followed a matrilineal system of kinship according to which the lineage was decided from the female's side. This meant that the place of women was influential within tribes, they were decision-makers and harbingers of the overall welfare of their society. It is notable here that often women owned land and property from their lineage. Women were not only engaged in agriculture but also in handicraft-making and other cultural activities. Along with fulfilling their agricultural tasks, women took care of their farm animals and helped great deal in maintaining the economic status of their community. The domain of handicrafts and textiles was primarily occupied by women who were skilled artisans. The vital role of women remained intact even by the western philosophy which came with the arrival of

Christianity in late 19th and early 20th century. When Nagaland became a part of India in the post-independence era, several initiatives were undertaken to make it an integral part of the country. Education and gender equality were promoted among the people and women actively participated in formal education leaving the taboos and societal norms behind.

Twentieth century witnessed the entry of Naga women into the fields of politics, entrepreneurship and education. A number of women leaders came forward to take the cudgels for the welfare of their society. According to an article -

"... Naga women are involving in the socio-economic and political scenario in the society. The coming of education played an important role among the women wherein they have attained a position and identity within the family and the community" (Resenmenla and Kinny 98).

The political participation of women increased significantly when many women came forward to act in local governance and administration. Still the challenges persisted, for the base of the society remains patriarchal, which hindered women from gaining equal opportunities. However, the constant efforts of Naga women prevailed which led the way for the establishment of different women's organizations and initiatives centered on women empowerment and their rights. **Kumar and Shobana** argue that, **"For the empowerment of women it is necessary to start working from grass root level so as to bear fruits of improvement"** (219). In the present time, Naga women are achieving great heights in various fields including entrepreneurship, politics, education and cultural activities. Women are making history by becoming the role models for future generations.

Main Text

Contribution of Naga women in Preservation of their Cultural Identity

Role in Politics

The matrilineal system of Nagaland society changed with the passage of time and the descent began to be decided from the line of the father; turning the society into chauvinist, patriarchal. Women lost the high status of prestige they had in every facet of their society. The first election of Nagaland Legislative Assembly took place in 1964; not a single female participated for a female leader. However, it was the year of 1977 which turned out to be a game changer for the female leadership in NLA. Rano M. Shaiza was the first woman of Nagaland to participate and win this election against a male counterpart for the first time, and she became the first woman MP for Lok Sabha in her state. A number of female leaders, inspired from her, followed the suit to lead the local governance of their state. The year 2022 saw Phangon Konyak elected as the president for Rajyasabha seat by Bhartiya Janta Party. And most recently the biggest history was achieved in this sphere when two women - Hekani Jakhalu Kense and Shalhoutuonuo Kruse became the first women MLAs from their state, both from Nationalist Democratic Progressive Party in power. Jakhalu is also the receiver of 'Nari Shakti Puraskar' for her initiatives in promoting gender equality. Below is the description of some eminent women of Nagaland who carved their names in the history of Nagaland politics: -

Rano M. Shaiza

Rano M. Shaiza, born Rano Iralu was a politician; a member of United Democratic Party. She was the first and only woman MP of Nagaland, a trailblazer and inspiration for the coming generation. Rano worked as a school teacher before engaging herself in the Naga separatist movement. In first general election of 1977, Rano defeated her opposite opponent, sitting Chief Minister Hokishe Sema, breaking the stereotypes of patriarchy. Rano M. Shaiza took many initiatives for the upliftment of women and the society of Nagaland. She was the founder of Naga Mother's Association (NMA) which was founded against the alcohol abuse in Nagaland. Her efforts were decisive in endorsing Nagaland Liquor Total Prohibition Act 1989, passed on 29 March 1990. Rano M. Shaiza thus opened the doors of future possibilities for Naga women.

Neidonuo Angami

Neidonuo Angami is one of the most active members of NMA, an NGO working for solving the social issues of Nagaland. Angami was born at the tumultuous time of Naga insurgency and lost her father who was a government official during this time. After a brief tenure as a sub-inspector in Kohima Police Force, Angami entered in teaching profession in 1972 and became instrumental in social services, founding Naga Weaver's Association. When Nagaland was inflicted by alcoholism and drug abuse a few women (mostly mothers) including Angami, formed Naga Mother's Association (NMA) - an NGO

which was formed to prohibit and tackle alcoholism and drug addiction causing violence in their state. She served as its general secretary and was responsible for the formation of NMA's subsequent sister organizations- NMA Youth and Women Welfare Organization (1986), Mt. Gilead Home (1989) and NMA HIV/AIDS Care Hospice (2001). Several campaigns are credited to increase her popularity as 'Shed No More Blood' which was started to provide a platform to the insurgents and prevailing politics to come on speaking terms. **Ajailiu Niumai** in her article '**Gender Among the Nagas of North East**' writes about her views on male support in women's political campaigns noted in an interview - "**She expressed that some men are skeptical and did not lend support to them**" (363). Her achievements and efforts are multidimensional. Indian government honored her by conferring on her 'Padma Shri' in 2000, the highest civilian award of the country.

Rosemary Dzuovichu

Rosemary Dzuovichu is a professor of English Literature at Nagaland University. She is currently an advisor of NMA and one of its active members. She undertook various initiatives for restoring peace in her state under the patronage of NMA. Together with her peace team Prof. Rosemary started off litigation which became responsible for 33 percent reservation of seats for women in urban bodies of Nagaland. Prof. Rosemary was awarded 2022 'Peace Channel Award' for her myriad efforts in peace building of her state.

Hekani Jakhalu Kense

Hekani Jakhalu Kense is a politician and social entrepreneur. Youth Net is an NGO set up by Jakhalu to open up career opportunities for the younger generation of Nagaland in their own state. Jakhalu was awarded prestigious Nari Shakti Puraskar (2018) for this initiative, making her the first woman of Nagaland to receive this honour. In 2023, Jakhalu Kense together with Shalhoutuonuo, made history by becoming the first woman MLA to be elected to the Nagaland Legislative Assembly.

Shalhoutuonuo Kruse

Shalhoutuonuo Kruse is a politician from Nagaland. Together with Hekani Jakhalu, she became the first woman from Nagaland to be elected to the Nagaland Constituent Assembly in 2023. Also, the candidate of NDPP, she won from the western Angami constituency. Thus, the state got two women MLAs who etched their names on the pages of Nagaland history. Presently, Kruse is a presiding minister of Women Resource Development & Horticulture in the 5th Rio Ministry, the first female to officiate such a post in the history of Nagaland.

Cultural Preservation and Development

Nagaland is a home to more than 17 ethnic tribes having their rich cultures and customs. Their rich cultural heritage is preserved in the oral traditions contained in their lores, decoded from the mnemonics and then transmitted orally from generation to generation. Nagaland is known for its textile designing, bamboo crafts and wooden pottery. Most of these activities are accomplished by females.

Clothing in Nagaland has a language of itself indicating the social status of men and women of a particular tribe they belonged. Women are playing massive role in preservation of their cultural heritage contained in their language, music, weaving and spinning and dancing etc. **Vitsou Yano** states in her article- "**Through different cultural activities in the society, Naga women have been carrying the identity of the Nagas in various walks of life from generation to generation**" (2).

Some notable women of Nagaland who strove to preserve and develop their culture: -

Tetseo Sisters

Tetseo Sisters is the name of a musical band of four sisters who blazed the trail for wide popularity of Nagaland's folk music. These four sisters are- Mutsevelu, Azine Veziolu, Kuvelu and Alune Tetseo. They got wide popularity not only for their rich traditional music but also their finely arrayed appearances in traditional attires makes them the focus of the audience during their performances.

Runway Nagaland

Runway Nagaland is a group of 25 women who come from socially and economically weaker background; belonging to different tribes of Nagaland. Its founder Nengneithem Hengna from Kuki tribe laid its foundation keeping in mind those women of Nagaland who are helpless and economically weaker in the society. These women create hand-made, customized jewelry from local natural materials. They also help preserve their culture by preparing handicrafts and textiles of local material and providing an online e market platform so that people of faraway lands can access the products they are making with diligence. It is the one of the brilliant efforts; it makes them economically independent as well as people come to appreciate their indigenous art and culture.

They work with the aim of promoting textile weaving tradition of Naga women along with ensuring a source of income which is sustainable as well as enhances the social, economic and cultural rights of these women weavers (Menezes).

Jesmima Zeliang

Jesmima Zeliang is the most successful entrepreneur and an inspiration for the women of North East. Zeliang is the founder of 'Heirloom Naga,' she revived the traditional loom practice of Nagaland and made it popular around the world. Her heirloom industry showcases the unique and rich culture of Naga society.

Social Contribution

Naga women play a crucial role in their society contributing to different aspects-agriculture, textile and weaving, crafts, education and healthcare and community welfare. Agricultural activities and tending to livestock and family have been the primary duties of Naga women. Additionally, women are the harbingers of traditional knowledge of their culture and its preservation in skills of music, art and storytelling. Earlier, women were deprived of many fundamental rights; the scenario is now changing with them gaining recognition for their role in decision-making process of their society through their entry into local governance and community welfare initiatives. During the period of insurgency educated women came forward for the help of their community even at the risk of their own lives. **Rita Manchanda** writes about the initiatives of Naga women in peace building of their state – **“Women have played a vital role in stopping violence throughout Naga history. As socially sanctioned peace-makers, women have historically intervened in the midst of battle and appealed for an end to violence”** (8).

Below is the description of some prominent women who made significant contribution to the social fabric of Naga society:

Dr. Temsula Ao

Dr. Temsula Ao was a writer and professor of English at North Eastern Hill University. She received 'Padma Shri' award for her contribution to literature and education. She also received 'Sahitya Akademi Award' for her book '*Laburnum For my Head.*' Dr. Temsula Ao was appointed the chairperson of the Nagaland State Commission for Women in 2013. Ao raised her voice against the plight of women and advocated for their rights in the Naga society. She wrote a number of short stories set during the period of unrest in Nagaland. These stories were published in the collection '*These Hills called Home: Stories from a War Zone.*' **Arenkala Ao** writes about the literary output of Temsula Ao – **“Besides the particular events in the stories, Ao does not fail to project women's heroic role during conflicts. Hence, through these fictional yet compelling stories, Ao brings out the other side of women, thereby not only creating a body of work but simultaneously delivering a message”** (27-28).

Lidi Kro-U

Lidi Kro-U is a women-led group formed to revive and promote the rich cultural treasure of Angami Naga tribe. They conduct training in hand-made materials as - bamboo basket weaving, headgear making, rice winnowing, and weaving of traditional clothes like shawls etc. for passing on the tradition to future generations. Many workshops are conducted for training by Lidi Kro-U on folk music, songs and drama.

Easterine Kire

Easterine Kire is presently a northern Norway based author of Nagaland. Most of her works are anchored against the backdrop of the lived experiences of the Nagas. The motivation behind her writing career was to give a concrete form to the oral narratives

and folk tales of Naga culture. She is in fact, the pioneer of modern Naga literature. Her first collection of poetry 'Kelhoukevira' was published in 1982. She is particularly notable for maintaining the essence of her mother tongue (Tenyimi); which is evident in her skilled usage of native expressions and terminologies in her literary works (Longkumer 13).

Monalisa Changkija

Monalisa Changkija is a journalist and poet of Nagaland. Monalisa has a versatile personality. While pursuing her career in journalism and literature, she was actively engaged in pursuits of the upliftment of her society. She was elected as a member of Working Group on Women's Empowerment in Indian National Planning Commission. She constantly wrote poems and short stories on unrest in Nagaland during insurgency. She is the only woman editor and publisher of the daily newspaper 'Nagaland Page.' Monalisa was involved in different initiatives as seminars and workshops across the country which centered around the issues of Naga women; their political rights, empowerment, human rights and other such programs (Ramthai and Mill 372).

Economic Contribution

The contribution of Naga women in economic landscape of their society is varied. Many women are actively engaged in agriculture, small-scale businesses like handicrafts and pottery. Agriculture is the primary domain of Naga women. Women in rural areas maintain the sustenance of their household along with agricultural activities. They involve in cultivation of crops, tending to farm animals, and small-scale agricultural businesses. Naga women are the chief preserver and weaver of their rich cultural tapestry. Women are diligently involved in handicrafts making and loin-weaving business which not only makes them economically independent but also helps them spreading their culture far and wide. The number of women entrepreneurs has increased significantly with the spread of awareness and education. It is noted that, **"During the last few years a welcome trend is seen in the growing interest among women to take up income generating activities, self-employment and entrepreneurship"** (Kiho and Jamir 820). Women led small-sized enterprises can be seen scattered throughout Nagaland. Thus, women are creating career opportunities as well as steering the growth of economy.

Conclusion To conclude, the preservation and development of their cultural heritage helped Naga women to uplift their social standing and preserve their own cultural identity as well. Naga women have a cultural identity which is multidimensional and has a deep influence on the values and existence of their particular tribe. It was the thing of past when they used to confine themselves to agriculture, they are now achieving success in different spheres of society, leading the progress of their state and spreading their culture and ethnic values far and wide. When in 2023 Nagaland announced the unprecedented election of the two first women MLAs in Nagaland Legislative Assembly, more opportunities and possibilities opened up for the females in the state. The status of Naga women has been undergoing dynamic changes since the arrival of Christianity and their integration into national framework; regardless of these challenges Naga women inadvertently brought about the transformation and development of their state. They continuously contributed for the cultural, social, economic growth of their society. The day is not far away when Naga women will definitely succeed integrating themselves in the mainstream of every sphere in their society and also of India.

- References**
1. Hornby, A. S. "Culture." Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary, edited by Diana Lea, Jennifer Bradbery, Victoria Bull, Leonie Hey, Stacey Bateman, Kallah Pridgeon, Gary Leicester, 10th ed., Oxford University Press, 2020, Print.
 2. Collier, M. J., Thomas, M. Cultural Identity: An Interpretive Perspective. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.1998
 3. Longchar, Resenmenla., Kinny, H. Salome. "Identity of Ao-Naga and Sumi-Naga Women as Gleaned from Folklores." *IRA – International Journal of Management & Social Sciences* 10. 03 (2018): 94-99. Web.
 4. Kumar, J. Suresh., Shobhana D. "Status of Women Empowerment in Nagaland." *International Journal of Advance and Innovative Research* 8.4 (2021): 217-222. Web.
 5. Niumai, Ajailiu. "Gender Among the Nagas of North East." *Gender Lens: Women's Issues and Perspectives*. Ed. Rekha Pande. Rawat Publisher, 2015. 346-376. Print.
 6. Yano, Vitsou. *Cultural World of Women in Angami Naga Society*. 2014. University of Hyderabad, Ph.D. Thesis.
 7. Menezes, Anisha. "Naga Tribal tradition kept alive by Runway Nagaland art collective." *The Hindu*, 17 Feb. 2020.
 8. Manchanda, Rita. "Naga Women Making a Difference: Peace Building in Northeastern India." *Hunt Alternatives Fund*. 2005. Web.
 9. Ao, Arenkula. "Language and Identity: With Reference to Naga Woman Writers." *Research Institute of Asian Women Sookmyung Women's University* 35. 4 (2019): 91-108. Web.

10. Longkumer, Watitula I. "Naga Women's Perspectives on Gender Roles: An Analysis of Literary Narratives." Zubaan Publishers Pvt. Ltd. 2019. Web.
11. Ranthami., Mili, Lakhimai." Resistance in Media and Literature: A study of Monalisa Changkija's Select Writings." *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research* 5. 11 (2018): pages. Web.
12. Kiho, Topeli K., Jamir, Imtilemla. "Women's Contribution towards Economic Development in Naga Society." *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology* 08. 08 (2023): 817-822.Web.